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Biodegradable albumen dielectrics for high-mobility MoS₂ phototransistors

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1 ABSTRACT

2 This work demonstrates the fabrication and characterization of single-layer MoS₂ field effect
3 transistors using biodegradable albumen (chicken eggwhite) as gate dielectric. By
4 introducing albumen as an insulator for MoS₂ transistors high carrier mobilities (up to ~90
5 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹) are observed, which is remarkably superior to that obtained with commonly used
6 SiO₂ dielectric which we attribute to ionic-gating due to the formation of an electric double
7 layer in the albumen MoS₂ interface. Additionally, the investigated devices are characterized
8 upon illumination, observing responsivities of 4.5 AW⁻¹ (operated in photogating regime)
9 and rise times as low as 52 ms (operated in photoconductivity regime). The presented study
10 reveals the combination of albumen with van der Waals materials for prospective
11 biodegradable and biocompatible optoelectronic device applications. Furthermore, the
12 demonstrated universal fabrication process can be easily adopted to fabricate albumen-based
13 devices with any other van der Waals material.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Two-dimensional (2D) semiconductors are promising candidates for next generation
3 electronics due to their ultrathin nature, exceptional electrical and optoelectronic properties,
4 and facile material combination beyond the limits of lattice matching. Out of the huge family
5 of semiconducting 2D materials, MoS₂ has been exploited in several proof of concept devices
6 ranging from field-effect transistors (FETs)¹⁻³, to photodetectors⁴⁻⁶ and memory devices⁷⁻
7 ¹⁰, just to name a few. These devices have found applications in many emerging applications
8 including neural computing, optoelectronics or the internet of things.¹¹⁻¹³

9 Although usually underestimated, the dielectric material is also a crucial part of these devices,
10 as their performance strongly depends on its properties. In FETs, for example, the dielectric
11 plays a major role in their scalability, power consumption and threshold electric field.¹⁴ Up
12 to now, SiO₂ has been heavily used as dielectric in 2D-based devices, mostly because of its
13 large availability in micro-fabrication processes but it does not provides optimal performance
14 in 2D devices. It is therefore equally important to invest research effort in finding suitable
15 dielectrics for 2D materials, optimized for different electronics and optoelectronics
16 applications.¹⁵ Pursuing high performance devices, dielectrics like hexagonal boron-nitride
17 (hBN), a 2D material with an atomically-flat surface and few dangling bonds, have been
18 studied in the last years.¹⁶ Many other insulators (2D as well as 3D) have been explored,
19 ranging from high-k materials, like HfO₂, ionic oxides, like CaF₂, and recently high-k free-
20 standing perovskites, as STO or BTO.^{15,17-21}

21 Because of the low toxicity and cytotoxicity of MoS₂,^{22,23} it is also being proposed for
22 biodegradable or even biocompatible electronics thus motivating the search for a

1 biocompatible dielectric material. From the various biocompatible dielectric materials tested
2 in the past, albumen has already showed good performance in organic FETs and memristive
3 devices.^{24–26} Albumen extracted directly from chicken eggs is mainly composed of water and
4 different types of protein. When spin-coated and thermally treated these amino acid chains
5 form a dielectric layer by natural denaturation.²⁷ The albumen integration and treatment is a
6 rather straight-forward process without the use of any filtering technique and results in
7 dielectric thicknesses of around 500 nm. The device structure aims to extend the 2D field-
8 effect transistor field to systems where biodegradability and biocompatibility is needed and
9 economical waste needs to be reduced with the possibility of usage in combination with
10 biodegradable flexible substrates.^{28–30} Albumen is probably one of the simplest
11 implementations of protein-based dielectrics with nearly endless opportunities in
12 combination with Van der Waals materials. Compared to other bio-materials a major
13 advantage is the resulting cost effectiveness stemming from the fact of the simple extraction
14 from chicken eggs without the need of chemical treatments, therefore reducing production
15 costs. To our knowledge, nobody has yet demonstrated an integration of albumen dielectrics
16 with van der Waals materials, which is the main goal of our work.

17 Here we present single-layer MoS₂ phototransistors using biodegradable albumen as gate
18 dielectric. We report that the fabricated devices exhibit orders of magnitude higher mobility
19 values ($\mu \sim 5\text{-}90 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) as compared with SiO₂-based devices ($\mu \sim 0.01\text{-}0.4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$).
20 Moreover, we report a fabrication technique that can be applied to any other van der Waals
21 material, and we demonstrate the optoelectronic response of the phototransistors ($R = 4.5$
22 AW^{-1} , $t_{\text{rise}} = 52 \text{ ms}$), giving a complete characterization of our albumen devices.

23

1 RESULTS

2 Device Fabrication

3 The albumen-based transistors are fabricated by drop-casting and spin-coating liquid
4 albumen onto a heavily doped silicon substrate followed by baking on the hotplate in two
5 steps of 10 min at 100°C and 120°C. Different albumen layer thicknesses can be obtained by
6 changing the spin coating speed (Fig. S1, Supporting Information). For better device stability
7 two layers of albumen were spin-coated on top of each other, following the same baking steps
8 after each coating and resulting in an overall thickness of ~500 nm (Fig. 1a,2). Subsequently,
9 Ti (5nm)/Au (45nm) source-drain electrodes were deposited by e-beam evaporation through
10 a shadow mask (Ossila, E321). The result is shown in Fig. 1a,3. Fig. 1b shows an optical
11 image of the gap between the source-drain contacts deposited onto the albumen layer. The
12 heavily doped silicon substrate underneath is used as a backgate electrode.

13 A single-layer MoS₂ flake was mechanically exfoliated from a bulk molybdenite crystal
14 (Molly Hill Mine, Quebec, Canada) onto a Gel-Film stamp (Gel-Film WF 4 × 6.0 mil by
15 Gel-Pack), followed by a dry deterministic transfer to build the channel between the Ti/Au
16 electrodes^{31,32}. Before transferring, the flake was characterized and identified as a monolayer
17 by differential reflectance measurement using a homebuilt micro-reflectance setup.³³ The
18 differential reflectance measurement including a comparison to another multilayer flake is
19 given in the supporting information (Fig. S2). Interestingly, we found that the MoS₂ adhesion
20 to albumen and gold was found to be even larger than that observed for devices featuring
21 SiO₂ dielectric, and the devices showed a very high conductivity even right after transfer
22 (without need of an additional annealing step). This is in striking contrast to SiO₂-based MoS₂

1 transistors where we have observed that after deterministic transfer the device conductivity
2 was rather poor and a vacuum annealing step is required. Raman and photoluminescence
3 measurements are proven tools to check the properties of 2D materials.³⁴⁻³⁶ These
4 measurements confirm that MoS₂'s material properties are preserved after transfer on top of
5 albumen. No changes in peak positions are observed compared to data taken from a SiO₂
6 substrate, excluding a possible functionalization of the 2D material (Supporting Information
7 Figure S3).^{37,38}

8 To better understand the function of the albumen insulating layer it is beneficial to review its
9 behavior during processing. The albumen is made up of about 90% water and 10% proteins.
10 Application of heat starts two commonly known processes: denaturation and coagulation.
11 Heating alters the amino acid chains by partially or completely unwinding the protein. This
12 process is called denaturation. Once a protein has denatured, it may meet and bind with
13 another denatured protein. When a sufficient number of denatured proteins are added
14 together, we are dealing with a coagulation phenomenon. In the egg, the coagulated proteins
15 form a three-dimensional layer that traps and immobilizes water. The most important
16 chemical reaction is the formation of disulfide bonds, between two cross-linked protein
17 molecules.²⁷ The protein disulfide bonds reduce the gate leakage current in the dielectric
18 layer of albumen FETs.³⁹ Interestingly, this cross-linked protein structure makes the albumen
19 dielectric very sturdy. We have found that, after baking, the albumen layer can withstand
20 acetone and 2-propanol treatment and remains electrically stable with no significant change
21 in leakage current. This opens up the possibility of employing a lithography/lift-off process
22 on top of the albumen, thereby enabling a wide range of post-processing techniques. We

1 address the reader to Supporting Information Figure S4 and S5 for details about the marker
2 lithography process.

3

4

5 **Figure 1: Fabrication of MoS₂ field effect transistors integrating eggwhite dielectric.** **a** Picture
6 of a bottle of liquid eggwhite and the three main processing stages of the substrate in chronological
7 order: a bare 2×1 cm² silicon substrate (1), a substrate with spin-coated and baked eggwhite thin film
8 (2), and a substrate with eggwhite dielectric after electrode evaporation (3). **b** Optical micrograph of
9 drain and source electrodes evaporated with a shadow mask onto the eggwhite dielectric. The scale
10 bar is 20 μm. **c** Optical micrograph of the electrodes shown in **b** after transferring a single-layer MoS₂
11 bridging the electrodes to create the semiconducting channel. (Inset) Transmission mode optical
12 microscopy image of the MoS₂ flake on the Gel-Film stamp ready for characterization and subsequent
13 dry-transfer.

14

15 **Electrical Analysis**

16 Electrical and optical device characterization were carried out using a homebuilt probe-
17 station setup under ambient conditions, allowing to perform current vs. voltage curve
18 characterization (*IVs* hereafter), transfer curve measurements and photocurrent
19 measurements. From these we can extract all necessary figures of merit for comparison with
20 other 2D transistors and phototransistors. In general, the fabrication and measurement of
21 devices showed an exceptional reproducibility with high yield in working devices. Fig. 2a,b
22 depicts the electrical characterization for one albumen transistor as an example of electrical
23 characterization. Gate voltage sweeps are comparably small for all devices in the range of -
24 10 to 10V, giving high tunability even with moderate low gate voltage values. The transfer

1 curve (displayed in a linear and logarithmic way in Fig. 2a) illustrates a high on-current. A
2 clear counter-clockwise hysteresis is observed in all measured albumen devices, ascribed to
3 the dielectric itself. As shown in other reported works, this counter-clockwise hysteresis is
4 attributed to an occurring polarization within the albumen layer^{25,40} and can be potentially
5 lowered by controlled moisture and oxygen levels of the measurement setup.²⁶ The inset in
6 Fig. 2b depicts the leakage current through the albumen layer, proofing the negligible
7 contribution to the device performance. Additionally, a more detailed leakage study confirms
8 that the albumen is electrically stable in a wide range of thicknesses and common humidities
9 (Supporting Information Figure S5). From the recorded data one can extract the low-field
10 field effect mobility by using the transfer curve slope and the expression

$$11 \quad \mu = \left[\frac{\partial I_{sd}}{\partial V_g} \right] \times \left[\frac{L}{W \cdot C' \cdot V_{sd}} \right], \quad (1)$$

12 Where L is the channel length, W is the channel width and C is the dielectric capacitance per
13 unit area. We performed capacitance measurements on multiple albumen films with different
14 contact areas as a function of frequency (Fig. 2c). By using the parallel plate capacitor
15 structure, we obtain a dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r = 11.2 \pm 1.9$. This value is slightly higher as
16 compared to other reported values²⁶, from which we calculate a capacitance per unit area C'
17 $= 13.7 \text{ nFcm}^{-2}$ (for more details regarding the full capacitance measurement from DC up to
18 1 MHz see Fig. S6 and S7 in the Supporting Information). This allows us to extract a mobility
19 of $\mu = 52.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for the device shown in Figure 2a. We also confirmed that the dielectric
20 constant values of the albumen layer do not change with thickness in the range of thicknesses
21 used in all devices, justifying the use of one dielectric constant for all calculations.

1 The detailed capacitance analysis shows that the average capacitance values tend to decrease
2 with increasing frequency and is maximum at DC. We also found that the parallel
3 conductance of the albumen dielectric is up to one order of magnitude higher than that
4 expected for an ideal solid-state capacitor. These two observations are compatible with the
5 presence of ionic current within the albumen, and thus the formation of an electric double
6 layer, typical of capacitors based on ionic materials.^{41,42} This mechanism would explain the
7 observed high mobility in the albumen-based MoS₂ transistor as it has been reported that
8 ionic-gating can improve the carrier mobility in MoS₂ reaching up to $\sim 100 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at room
9 temperature, inducing ionic-gating rather than solid state electric field-effect.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ Schottky
10 contact behavior can be observed in Fig. 2b, resulting from the Au/MoS₂ interface. However,
11 according to other works ionic gating allows to largely dope the MoS₂ channel, thus reducing
12 the Schottky barrier and allowing high mobility values.⁴³ To confirm a reduced Schottky
13 barrier we have performed and compared in-operando Kelvin probe force microscopy
14 measurements (KPFM) of an MoS₂-flake on top of albumen and SiO₂ under different source-
15 drain bias voltages. Visualizing the potential drop from electrode to electrode over the MoS₂
16 channel and subtracting the recorded zero-bias potential to remove the work function
17 difference from the electrostatic profile, allows us to extract the Schottky barrier for both
18 cases. We observed half of the barrier height on top of albumen compared to SiO₂. The results
19 still show a noticeable Schottky barrier, hence explaining the non-linear *IV* curves. We
20 forward the reader to the Supporting Information for the details of those measurements.

21 The mobility values for all fabricated devices can be calculated and plotted together with the
22 corresponding ON/OFF current ratios (Fig. 2d). Device parameters and extracted values,
23 including transconductance and carrier concentration values, as well as all *IV* curves and

1 transfer curves are given in the supporting information (Table S1, Fig. S9-S16). Apart from
2 consistent counter-clockwise hysteresis, the measured transfer curves show device-to-device
3 variations stemming from the fact that devices have been fabricated with different batches of
4 albumen sources of same origin without filtering techniques. The calculated mobility values
5 for all albumen devices are in the range of $5\text{-}89\text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ which is comparably high with
6 respect to standard single-layer MoS_2 transistors with SiO_2 dielectrics, as expected for ionic-
7 gated devices. To further proof the significant increase in mobility we fabricated multiple
8 transistors choosing SiO_2 as the insulating material, following the same protocol as for the
9 albumen-based transistor. SiO_2 is still the most commonly deployed dielectric material in 2D
10 semiconductor devices due to its widely usage in semiconductor industry. To ensure a
11 comprehensive outcome the same materials and processing steps were employed for the
12 SiO_2 -based transistors, simply changing the substrate to a Si/SiO_2 one with an oxide thickness
13 of 285 nm. After performing the same electrical measurements with the SiO_2 devices, clearly
14 knowing its dielectric constant ($\epsilon_r = 3.9$), the values for ON/OFF current ratios and mobilities
15 can be calculated. These values are plotted next to the albumen device values (Fig. 2d). SiO_2 -
16 based transistor device parameters and selected transfer curves in similar fashion to the
17 albumen devices are given in the supporting information (Table S2, Fig. S17). It is clearly
18 shown that the albumen transistors exhibit orders of magnitude higher mobility values by
19 keeping the same range of ON/OFF current ratios compared to the SiO_2 counterparts.
20 Surprisingly this is true for all fabricated devices with absolutely every albumen transistor
21 outperforming any SiO_2 one, although all the SiO_2 devices have been thermally annealed in
22 vacuum conditions at 200°C for at least 2 h prior to measuring, which was not needed for the
23 albumen devices. It is important to note, that all devices were measured at ambient conditions
24 in two-terminal setup configuration, without removing contact resistance. Hence the

1 calculated mobility reported here are lower bound estimates which explains why our SiO₂-
 2 based device mobilities are comparably low to what is reported in other works.^{1,46,47} It is
 3 worth noting, that all devices are non-encapsulated and therefore very sensitive to ambient
 4 conditions (as well seen with similar values in other works^{46,48,49}), explaining the poor
 5 mobility values and further highlighting the improved characteristics of the albumen devices.
 6 We have observed that the mobility of SiO₂-based MoS₂ transistors quickly degrade upon air
 7 exposure after vacuum annealing. As it is beyond the scope of the current publication, it will
 8 be reported elsewhere. All SiO₂-based devices show typical clockwise hysteresis, which once
 9 again supports the claim of attributing the counter-clockwise hysteresis of the albumen
 10 devices to the dielectric itself.

11

12 **Figure 2: Electrical device characterization of MoS₂ field effect transistors with eggwhite**
 13 **dielectric. a** Transfer curves (I_{sd} vs. V_g) plotted in linear and semi-logarithmic (inset) fashion.
 14 **b** Corresponding current vs. voltage curves (IVs) for different gate voltages ranging from -10 to 10V.

1 The inset shows gate leakage current for the used gate voltage range. **c** Relative dielectric constant
2 plotted as a function of frequency for 1 mm² area (blue) and 4 mm² area (green) albumen capacitors.
3 **d** An overview of all fabricated albumen-based transistors (blue) in comparison to SiO₂-based
4 transistors (red). The albumen-based devices show significant higher mobility values and similar
5 ON/OFF current ratios than SiO₂-based ones. Full stars correspond to devices fabricated with bottled
6 pasteurized eggwhite and empty stars to the ones made out of eggwhite extracted from whole chicken
7 eggs.

8

9 **Optoelectronic analysis**

10 As MoS₂ is also a promising material for optoelectronic applications, it is of interest to test
11 the response of the albumen-based devices to external illumination. Fig. 3a shows the
12 photocurrent of an albumen-based MoS₂ device, at zero gate voltage, for an illumination with
13 a 660 nm LED light switched On (10 s) and Off (10 s), displaying rather steep rise/fall times.
14 Changing the gate voltage leads to a remarkable change in the rise/fall times, as increased
15 doping level is known to lead to a dominant role of photogating photocurrent generation
16 mechanism. This effect can be described by the two main mechanisms contributing to the
17 photoresponse of an MoS₂-based device: the photogating effect (higher responsivity, slower
18 response) and the photoconductive effect (lower responsivity, faster response), where the
19 first one has been attributed to a shift in threshold voltage of the transistor and the second
20 one to hole trapping.⁵⁰⁻⁵² For negative gate voltages, where the dominant photocurrent
21 generation mechanism is the photo-conductive effect, the responsivity is lower, but the
22 rise/fall times becomes much faster. The inset in Fig. 3a displays this behavior with a
23 measured rise time of 54 ms under a gate bias of -5 V and an increase in response time to 33
24 s for a positive gate voltage of +5 V. Although a positive gate voltage means a slower device
25 response it also gives rise to better responsivity values due to the dominant photo-gating
26 effect. The power-dependent responsivity values of the device for gate voltages of zero and
27 +5 V are shown in Fig. 3b. The transistor's responsivity to light rises as the gate bias is

1 increased, with a peak of 4.5 AW^{-1} at $V_g = +5 \text{ V}$ and a LED power density of 2 mWcm^{-2} . This
2 responsivity value can be considered high compared to other studies of MoS_2 -flake-based
3 phototransistors, usually ranging between 0.008 and 0.57 AW^{-1} , whereas response times are
4 in the same range.^{48,53} Reports with higher responsivity values make use of more
5 sophisticated device structures, much higher bias- and gate-voltages, or multi-layer MoS_2
6 configurations.^{4,54-56} We also characterize the spectral response of our albumen-based device
7 by measuring the photocurrent while sweeping the wavelength over the $500\text{-}750 \text{ nm}$ range.
8 This measurement shows two prominent peak responses at A- and B-exciton energies of
9 MoS_2 (Fig. 3c) followed for a vanishing photocurrent for illumination with energies lower
10 than the A exciton. For better illustration the same graph shows the differential reflectance
11 measurement of the monolayer flake prior to transfer from the Gel-Film stamp, distinctly
12 displaying its excitonic response and additionally confirming the single-layer thickness.

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Figure 3: Optoelectronic characterization of MoS₂ field effect transistors integrating eggwhite dielectric. **a** Photoresponse under pulsed LED illumination of 660 nm wavelength ($V_g = -5$ V, $V_{bias} = 1$ V, LED power density 75.6 mW/cm²). On and off illumination times are 10 s. (Inset) Rise time, extracted from measurements under pulsed illumination like that shown in **a**, as a function of the gate voltage. **b** Responsivity as a function of the illumination power density under 660 nm LED emission ($V_{bias} = 1$ V). **c** Wavelength dependence of the photocurrent showing an enhanced photoresponse at MoS₂'s excitonic energies ($V_{bias} = 1$ V). For comparison the measured differential reflectance spectrum of the MoS₂ flake prior transfer is added to the plot, relating A (660 nm) and B (610 nm) exciton peaks to the peak responses in photocurrent measurements.

12 At this point it would be natural to wonder what would happen if one used the whole egg as
13 a dielectric instead of just the albumen. For that reason, we fabricated another set of devices
14 applying the same process steps, but this time using a mixture of albumen and yolk as the
15 dielectric layer. The resulting devices still show transistor behavior both in electrical and
16 optoelectronic characterization, but expectedly exhibit a lot of gate leakage and therefore

1 perform not like the albumen-based ones. We forward the reader to the Supporting
2 Information Figure S18 for details about the whole egg MoS₂ transistors.

3

4 **DISCUSSION**

5 In summary, we present the use of albumen dielectrics in combination with single-layer MoS₂
6 to realize field effect transistors, as a first step to biocompatible device applications with
7 semiconducting van der Waals materials. Compared to traditional SiO₂-dielectric based
8 devices, we not only confirmed a higher dielectric constant ($\epsilon_r = 11.2 \pm 1.9$), but the results
9 also indicate a major advantage in mobility values, with mobilities reaching up to $\sim 90 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}$
10 s^{-1} . Optoelectronic device characterization revealed responsivities of $R = 4.5 \text{ AW}^{-1}$ and rise
11 times of $t_{\text{rise}} = 52 \text{ ms}$. Furthermore, the fabrication procedure demonstrated, can be applied in
12 any other combination with van der Waals materials due to its universal nature. Albumen's
13 resistivity to chemicals used in standard lithography and lift-off processes additionally opens
14 a world of post-processing techniques that can even lead to more complex devices. Our work
15 demonstrates the combination of albumen dielectrics with two-dimensional van der Waals
16 materials, introducing a new platform for biodegradable 2D applications.

17

18 **METHODS**

19 **Materials and albumen dielectric fabrication**

20 Liquid eggwhite was prepared unfiltered for spin-coating from two different sources: from
21 bottled pasteurized eggwhite (Mercadona, Huevos Guillén S.L.) and from whole chicken
22 eggs after separation of yolk and eggwhite using a kitchen strainer. MoS₂ flakes were

1 obtained from natural molybdenite mineral (Molly Hill Mine, Quebec, Canada) by
2 mechanical exfoliation using Nitto tape (Nitto SPV 224).

3 Eggwhite typically consists of liquid and coagulated albumen. Only the liquid part is used
4 for the spin coating process, as it results in a thinner and more homogenous film. The
5 unfiltered liquid eggwhite was drop-casted and spin-coated onto the silicon substrate using a
6 rate of 4000 rpm for 40 s. Subsequently it was baked on a hot plate at 100°C for 10 min and
7 120°C for 10 min. If necessary, the procedure can be repeated for a second layer and higher
8 rpm, resulting in a more stable insulating layer.

9 **Electrode Deposition**

10 Prepatterned gold electrodes were fabricated by evaporation of 5 nm Ti (used as adhesion
11 layer) and 45 nm Au onto a SiO₂ (285 nm)/Si (p++) substrate through a shadow mask (Ossila,
12 E321) in an electron-beam evaporator system.

13 **Electrical Characterization**

14 All electrical characterizations of devices were carried out in a home-built measurement
15 setup under ambient conditions. A source-meter unit (Keithley 2450) was used for
16 performing the electrical measurements between source and drain electrodes. Two TENMA
17 programmable benchtop power supplies (model 72-2715) are connected in parallel to
18 perform gate voltage sweeps between -10 V and +10 V.

19 **Optoelectronic Characterization**

20 The photoresponse of the albumen devices was tested with a home-built probe station
21 operating at room temperature in ambient conditions. The system is connected to a Keithley
22 2450 source-measure unit to measure the electrical transport. For the optical excitation we
23 recur to multimode fiber-coupled light sources, attached to the optical inspection system.

1 This allows us to produce a circular spot of 850 μm in diameter with homogeneous power
2 density over the sample. We employed one LED source (Thorlabs, MxxxFy series) of 660
3 nm wavelength to study the power-dependent photocurrent generation and a Xenon lamp
4 with an integrated monochromator (Bentham TLS120Xe) to test the photo-response at
5 different illumination conditions.

6 **KPFM Characterization**

7 A commercial Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) system, from CSI Instrument, operating in
8 ambient conditions was employed to perform morphological and surface potential (KPFM)
9 characterization of the samples. Measurements have been acquired in dynamic mode, using
10 the amplitude as the feedback channel for topography acquisition. Surface potential maps
11 have been measured using single pass KFM mode (HD-KFM) with PtSi-coated tip from
12 Nanosensors (PtSi-FM). Vac voltage for KPFM measurements was applied to the tip,
13 $V_{ac}=1\text{V}$. Image analysis was performed with the Gwyddion free software. A Keithley 2450
14 source-measure unit was used to apply different bias voltages between the Au electrodes.

15

16 **DATA AVAILIBILTY**

17 The data of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

18

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8

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13 **Author Contributions**

14 T.P. fabricated, measured and analysed the albumen-based devices, performed thickness
15 characterization and albumen-based lithography and carried out merit calculations. P.B. and
16 Y.X. fabricated, measured and analysed the SiO₂-based devices. F.P., E.D. and G.F.
17 performed the dielectric capacitance characterization. A.C.-G. conceived the experiment.
18 A.C.-G. and G.F. supervised the experiments. T.P. and A.C.-G. drafted the first version of
19 the manuscript. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

20 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

21 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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- 24

1

2 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

3 **Figure 1: Fabrication of MoS₂ field effect transistors integrating eggwhite dielectric.** **a** Picture
4 of a bottle of liquid eggwhite and the three main processing stages of the substrate in chronological
5 order: a bare 2×1 cm² silicon substrate (1), a substrate with spin-coated and baked eggwhite thin film
6 (2), and a substrate with eggwhite dielectric after electrode evaporation (3). **b** Optical micrograph of
7 drain and source electrodes evaporated with a shadow mask onto the eggwhite dielectric. The scale
8 bar is 20 μm. **c** Optical micrograph of the electrodes shown in **b** after transferring a single-layer MoS₂
9 bridging the electrodes to create the semiconducting channel. (Inset) Transmission mode optical
10 microscopy image of the MoS₂ flake on the Gel-Film stamp ready for characterization and subsequent
11 dry-transfer.

12 **Figure 2: Electrical device characterization of MoS₂ field effect transistors with eggwhite**
13 **dielectric.** **a** Transfer curves (I_{sd} vs. V_g) plotted in linear and semi-logarithmic (inset) fashion. **b**
14 Corresponding current vs. voltage curves (IVs) for different gate voltages ranging from -10 to 10V.
15 The inset shows gate leakage current for the used gate voltage range. **c** Relative dielectric constant
16 plotted as a function of frequency for 1 mm² area (blue) and 4 mm² area (green) albumen capacitors.
17 **d** An overview of all fabricated albumen-based transistors (blue) in comparison to SiO₂-based
18 transistors (red). The albumen-based devices show significant higher mobility values and similar
19 ON/OFF current ratios than SiO₂-based ones. Full stars correspond to devices fabricated with bottled
20 pasteurized eggwhite and empty stars to the ones made out of eggwhite extracted from whole chicken
21 eggs.

22 **Figure 3: Optoelectronic characterization of MoS₂ field effect transistors integrating eggwhite**
23 **dielectric.** **a** Photoresponse under pulsed LED illumination of 660 nm wavelength ($V_g = -5$ V, $V_{bias} = 1$
24 V, LED power density 75.6 mW/cm²). On and off illumination times are 10 s. (Inset) Rise time,
25 extracted from measurements under pulsed illumination like that shown in **a**, as a function of the gate
26 voltage. **b** Responsivity as a function of the illumination power density under 660 nm LED emission
27 ($V_{bias} = 1$ V). **c** Wavelength dependence of the photocurrent showing an enhanced photoresponse at
28 MoS₂'s excitonic energies ($V_{bias} = 1$ V). For comparison the measured differential reflectance spectrum
29 of the MoS₂ flake prior transfer is added to the plot, relating A (660 nm) and B (610 nm) exciton
30 peaks to the peak responses in photocurrent measurements.

31

32

Supporting Information:

Biodegradable albumen dielectrics for high-mobility MoS₂ phototransistors

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1

2 To do a fast determination of albumen thickness we use differential reflectance
3 measurements with a spectrometer and Fresnel's equations to fit the measured data. The
4 refractive index of eggwhite is 1.5, which allows to calculate the optical contrast using a
5 reflectance measurement of the bare silicon substrate and a reflectance measurement of the
6 spin-coated and baked eggwhite. By fitting the optical contrast to the calculated Fresnel
7 contrast we can easily and quickly determine the albumen layer thickness. We used different
8 spinning speeds and determined each thickness with the spectrometer measurements.
9 Afterwards we did AFM thickness measurements to compare these values to the fitted ones
10 and get a very good agreement with the calculated data, which justifies the application of the
11 fast contrast method. Figure S1 gives thickness values for the range 3000-6000rpm measured
12 with AFM and fitted with the spectra, as well as exemplary contrast fits for 3k and 6k
13 spinning speeds.

1

2 **Figure S1: Albumen film thickness determination methods.** Different spin-coating speeds are
 3 compared by reflectance spectrometer measurements and AFM measurements, proving the reliability
 4 of fast spectrometer thickness determination. The reflectance data is fitted using Fresnel's equations.
 5 The fits for two spin-coating speeds (3000 and 6000 rpm) are shown on the right, giving a good
 6 agreement between experimentally measured reflectance and the expected Fresnel curves.

7

8 To confirm the monolayer thickness of the used flakes we measure the different thicknesses
 9 of a multilayer flake for comparison in Fig. S2. The used monolayer of albumen transistor
 10 #18 is depicted in Fig. S2a and its corresponding differential reflectance measurement in Fig.
 11 S2b. A multilayer flake for comparing measurements is shown in Fig. S2c. Three different
 12 layers of this flake were measured, monolayer (1L), bilayer (2L) and three-layer
 13 configuration (3L). Comparing the reflectance measurement of our used flake and the
 14 measurements obtained from the multilayer flake, it is clear that we can easily identify our
 15 flakes as monolayers prior to transfer. Note that the bilayer measurement illustrates the
 16 existence of the interlayer exciton, confirming further our point.

1

2 **Figure S2: Differential reflectance measurements of MoS₂ layers.** (a) Optical microscope image
 3 of monolayer MoS₂ before transfer on the albumen substrate. (b) Differential reflectance
 4 measurement of flake in (a). (c) Optical microscope image of MoS₂ flake with multiple layer
 5 thicknesses. (d) Differential reflectance measurements of monolayer (1L), bilayer (2L) and three-
 6 layer part (3L) of flake from (c).

7

8

9 **Figure S3: Raman and PL measurements of MoS₂ layers.** (a) Raman spectroscopy characterization
 10 of monolayer MoS₂ on an albumen substrate and a SiO₂ substrate. (b) Photoluminescence
 11 characterization of the same monolayers MoS₂ for each substrate. The excitation wavelength of the
 12 system is 532 nm.

13

1 For demonstration purposes an easy marker-process was tested, using a commercial marker
 2 pen to apply an evaporation mask on a processed substrate with an albumen layer on top. The
 3 mask was created by simply drawing a line with the marker pen. In the following step a layer
 4 of 50 nm gold was evaporated onto the substrate. For the lift-off the substrate was left in
 5 acetone for 10 min, rinsed with 2-propanol and blow-dried with a nitrogen gun. Electrical
 6 leakage characterization was carried out to confirm the stability of albumen after immersion
 7 in Acetone. A sample of albumen with top gold contacts was immersed in Acetone and rinsed
 8 in Isopropanol for different times with leakage current measurements after each immersion.
 9 The albumen layer does not get damaged by the lift-off process (Fig. S5c).

10

11 **Figure S4: Marker lithography process.** Panels (a)-(d) show the used procedure to realize patterned
 12 gold films on albumen films, making use of albumen's resilience against acetone and 2-propanol. (a)
 13 Spin-coating and baking of a 300 nm thick albumen film on a Si substrate. (b) Structuring desired
 14 patterns using a commercial marker pen with a tip width of 0.75 mm. After the pattern is applied a
 15 50 nm layer of gold is evaporated using an electron beam evaporation system. (c) Lift-off in an
 16 acetone bath. (d) The gold layer is structured while the albumen layer is unharmed. Microscope
 17 images of different steps show the albumen layer before processing (e), the albumen layer covered
 18 with a marker line (f) and the substrate after lift-off, demonstrating the intact albumen film and
 19 patterned gold structures.

20

1

2 **Figure S5: Leakage current characterization.** (a) Thickness dependent leakage current of one
 3 series of albumen samples from the same egg with thicknesses ranging from 370 nm to 600 nm. (b)
 4 Humidity dependent leakage current for an albumen layer of 550 nm thickness in the range of 10-50
 5 % humidity. (c) Changes of leakage current for an albumen layer of 550 nm thickness for different
 6 immersion times in Acetone and subsequent rinsing in Isopropanol are shown up to a time of 30 min.
 7 The inset shows the maximum leakage current values for under a bias of 10 V. All samples have an
 8 effective electrode area of 1 x 1 mm².

9

10

11 To fully understand the electrical properties of the albumen dielectric, several capacitors with
 12 different active areas have been defined. The albumen capacitors were fabricated on a highly
 13 doped silicon substrate, which acts as the bottom electrode, and exploiting a top electrode
 14 with evaporated gold contact. The electrical characterization has been performed modelling
 15 the capacitor with an R_p - C_p parallel model as shown in Figure S6a, with R_p taking into
 16 account the leakage through the dielectric. The effects of the series resistance were neglected,
 17 considering the high conductivity of the electrodes.

18 C_p and R_p values have been estimated by characterizing the capacitors as a function of
 19 frequency, down to the DC. In particular, the AC measurements have been performed with
 20 an LCR meter (KEYSIGHT E4989A) using a four-probe configuration, in the frequency
 21 range 100Hz - 2MHz, while applying a sinusoidal signal with amplitude equal to 1 V. An

1 open circuit calibration has been performed before each data acquisition to ensure
2 measurement accuracy.

3 For the DC characterization, the circuit shown in Fig. S6a has been exploited, where the
4 Device Under Test (DUT) has been connected between the inverting input and the output of
5 a low-noise operational amplifier (Op-Amp) (LF356N). The chosen amplifier also ensures
6 that the bias current generators can be neglected with respect to the bias current I_p of the
7 DUT, which is further generated by the series of a DC voltage V_p and the resistor $R = 10 \text{ M}\Omega$
8 (i.e., $I_p = V_p/R$). Before the measurement, the switch is closed, so that the current I_p flows
9 through the switch. At $t = 0 \text{ s}$, the switch is opened, and I_p flows through the DUT. The
10 generated voltage transient across the DUT, and hence at the output, has been monitored by
11 means of an oscilloscope connected to the output of the circuit.

12 The values of the capacitance and of the resistance have been estimated, fitting the output
13 characteristic through the function:

$$14 \quad f(t) = I_p R_p \left(1 - e^{-t/R_p C_p} \right),$$

15 as indicated in Fig. S6b. For the characterization, DC voltage values between 0.4 V to 0.8 V
16 have been chosen. An open circuit calibration has been performed before each data
17 acquisition in order to evaluate the parasitic capacitance of the system, which can be
18 considered as an offset in the capacitor measurements.

19

Figure S6: (a) Electric circuit used for the DC characterization of the capacitor, considered as the parallel of a resistor R_p and a Capacitance C_p . (b) R_p and C_p are extracted through a fitting procedure of the output voltage V_{out} as a function of time with the analytical formula shown in figure.

6 The results of the AC and DC characterizations as a function of frequency are shown in

7 Figure S7. To evaluate the dispersion of the device characteristics, several capacitors have

8 been measured, with areas of 1 mm x 1 mm and 2 mm x 2 mm. Fig. S5a and S5b show the

9 capacitance and the parallel conductance values ($G_p = 1/R_p$) per unit area, as a function of the

10 frequency. Fig. S7c shows the values of the ratio between the capacitive susceptance and the

11 parallel conductance: this ratio is an indication of the quality of the capacitors, i.e., a higher

12 ratio represents a device closer to the ideal, where the leakage through the dielectric can be

13 neglected. Generally, this value is not very high, indicating that losses in the devices are not

14 negligible. This is expected in a capacitor based on an ionic conductor material where ion

15 current would explain the high parallel conductance.

16 Fig. S7a shows that the average capacitance value tends to decrease with increasing

17 frequency and is maximum at DC: this trend might be compatible with the presence of an

18 electric double layer, typical of capacitors based on ionic materials.

1 The dielectric constant values as a function of the frequency were derived using the parallel
2 plate capacitor equation:

3
$$\epsilon_r = C_p t / A \epsilon_0,$$

4 where A is area of the capacitor, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity ($8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ AsV}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$), while
5 an average thickness (t) equal to 725 nm of the albumen dielectric layer has been considered.
6 Additionally, another batch of albumen capacitors with different thicknesses was measured
7 to evaluate the effect of dielectric thickness on the capacitance and dielectric constant. The
8 plots show that in a thickness range of 370-600 nm the dielectric constant does not depend
9 on the thickness of the albumen layer. Especially the DC dielectric constant values are
10 showing no change depending on the thickness.

1

2 **Figure S7: Capacitance measurements of albumen thin films.** (a) Measured capacitance values
 3 per unit area plotted as a function of frequency; (b) measured conductance values per unit area plotted
 4 as a function of frequency; (c) reactive over real part ratio of the measured admittance plotted as a
 5 function of frequency. All the measured values are referred to 1 mm^2 area (blue line) and 4 mm^2 area
 6 (green line) albumen capacitors. The error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean collected
 7 values. (d) Permittivity vs. frequency plots for a batch of albumen capacitors with different
 8 thicknesses and same top electrode size for thickness dependent capacitance analysis. Thicknesses
 9 are labelled in the plot.

10

1

2 **Figure S8: KPFM measurements for Schottky barrier analysis.** (a) and (c) Recorded topography
 3 images of the two devices on SiO₂ and albumen, respectively. (b) and (d) Recorded surface potential
 4 maps of both devices for different source-drain biases (0 V, 0.5 V and 1.5 V). The left electrode is
 5 grounded. Potential profile lines are indicated in white. (e) Schottky barrier plots for both cases and
 6 voltages. The potential profiles extracted from (b) and (d) are shown as insets, with dotted lines
 7 marking the MoS₂-area of the profile. The barrier plots result from subtracting the zero-bias profile
 8 from the desired voltage profile. The barrier height is the difference between the potential of the gold
 9 electrode and the potential of the MoS₂ flake at the border.

10

11 Dimensions and electrical device properties of all measured albumen transistors:

Nr.	W (μm)	L (μm)	On/off ratio	g_m ($\text{A}\cdot\text{V}^{-1}$)	Mobility ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)	V_{TH} (V)	V_{gm} (V)	$n_{2\text{D}}$ (cm^{-2})
6	15	30	3×10^2	6×10^{-7}	56.9	6	7.5	1.97×10^{11}
8	20	25	1.7×10^3	1.3×10^{-7}	7.7	3	6	3.95×10^{11}

9	7	25	5×10^2	3.1×10^{-7}	52.5	-3	2	6.58×10^{11}
10	20	25	1×10^4	1.5×10^{-6}	88.9	2	5.5	4.61×10^{11}
14	12	35	2×10^3	3.5×10^{-7}	48.4	4	6	2.63×10^{11}
16	11	25	3×10^2	7.9×10^{-8}	9.1	1	3	2.47×10^{11}
18	7.5	25	2×10^2	5×10^{-7}	84.1	6	8.5	3.09×10^{11}
20	20	25	4×10^3	1.2×10^{-6}	75.7	6	7	1.24×10^{11}
24*	12	25	7.6×10^2	3×10^{-7}	32.0	7	8.5	1.86×10^{11}
25*	11	27	1.5×10^1	4.4×10^{-8}	5.5	7	9.5	3.09×10^{11}

1

2 **Table S1: Device geometries and electrical figures of merit of the albumen transistors.** Values
3 are extracted for all fabricated albumen transistors. Mobility, transconductance, threshold voltage and
4 transconductance voltage values are corresponding to the forward sweep. Devices 24 and 25 are
5 fabricated with eggwhite extracted from whole eggs, all other devices from bottled pasteurized
6 eggwhite.

7 Electrical device properties of all measured SiO₂-based transistors:

Nr.	On/off ratio	g_m (AV ⁻¹)	Mobility (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	V _{TH} (V)	V _{gm} (V)	n _{2D} (cm ⁻²)
1	1.35×10^3	5×10^{-9}	0.4	-33	19	3.86×10^{12}
2	2×10^1	8×10^{-11}	0.002	-50	0	3.71×10^{12}
3	2.5×10^2	8×10^{-10}	0.037	-25	21	3.42×10^{12}
4	2.35×10^3	1.3×10^{-9}	0.08	-19	18	2.75×10^{12}
5	5.75	5.85×10^{-11}	0.012	-26	29	4.09×10^{12}
6	3.7	1.8×10^{-11}	0.002	-30	6	2.67×10^{12}
7	3.75×10^3	5.67×10^{-10}	0.01	-26	1	2.01×10^{12}
8	9×10^1	2.69×10^{-10}	0.011	-16	28	3.27×10^{12}
9	5	1.02×10^{-10}	0.003	-14	18	2.38×10^{12}
10	3×10^1	7.36×10^{-12}	0.0004	-5	19	1.78×10^{12}
11	4×10^1	3.44×10^{-10}	0.021	-10	9	1.41×10^{12}
12	2.7×10^2	5.48×10^{-11}	0.065	-19	13	2.38×10^{12}
13	5	2.03×10^{-10}	0.01	-20	16	2.67×10^{12}
14	1.6×10^4	4.18×10^{-9}	0.033	-24	-1	1.71×10^{12}
15	1.65×10^3	3.87×10^{-10}	0.023	-22	16	2.82×10^{12}
16	1.5×10^2	7.36×10^{-12}	0.004	-5	16	1.56×10^{12}

8

9 **Table S2: Electrical figures of merit of the SiO₂-based transistors.** Values are extracted for all
10 fabricated SiO₂-based transistors. Mobility, transconductance, threshold voltage and
11 transconductance voltage values are corresponding to the forward sweep.

12

13

14 In the following the characteristic electrical measurements for all albumen devices are given,

15 with the (a) panels showing the current vs. voltage (*IV*) curves for gate voltage sweeps of -

1 10 to 10 V and the (b) panels showing the corresponding transfer curves in linear and
2 logarithmic fashion for the same gate bias range. Numbers correspond to the label in Table
3 S1. The curves of the albumen transistor with the number 9 are displayed in the main text.

4

5

6 **Figure S9: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #6.**

7

8

9 **Figure S10: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #8.**

10

1

2 **Figure S11: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #10.**

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5 **Figure S12: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #14.**

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8 **Figure S13: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #16.**

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3 **Figure S14: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #18.**

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6 **Figure S15: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #20.**

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8

1 **Figure S16: Electrical measurements of albumen transistor #24.**

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3

4 **Figure S17: Transfer curves of selected SiO₂-based devices.** Panels (a)-(d) show the transfer
5 curves of devices 4, 7, 14 and 15, respectively, corresponding to the labels in Table S2. The insets
6 show the curves in semi-logarithmic plots. Source-drain voltages for all measurements are $V_{ds} = 1V$.
7 All curves show clockwise hysteresis.

8

9 To confirm the use of only albumen from the whole egg and neglect the yolk, whole egg
10 dielectric transistors were fabricated. Fabrication steps are exactly the same as before, but
11 this time using the liquid parts of both the albumen and the yolk of a whole chicken egg and
12 stirring them until fully combined (Fig. S18a). The finished transistor is depicted in Fig. S18b
13 and shows the MoS₂ channel between source-drain electrodes on top of two layers of egg
14 spin-coated subsequently. The egg layer is visually more cracked after fabrication than it was
15 the case for solely albumen. Electrical analysis shows the possibility of tuning the channel

1 but also reveals big amounts of gate leakage, seen in the current vs. voltage characteristics as
 2 an offset voltage (Fig. S18c). Subtracting the offset from the data it is possible to plot the
 3 transfer curve of the egg transistors (Fig. S18d). Though the FET does not show optimal
 4 behavior it is still possible to measure photo response at zero gate voltage. The corresponding
 5 measurements are depicted in Fig. S18e and once again indicate MoS₂'s excitonic A and B
 6 peaks.

7
 8 **Figure S18: Phototransistors using complete egg dielectric.** (a) Chosen dielectric material out of
 9 whole chicken eggs (mixture of the liquid parts of eggwhite and yolk). (b) Optical micrograph of the
 10 finished device after MoS₂ transfer. The baked egg dielectric separates the silicon back gate from the
 11 semiconductor channel. (c) Current vs. voltage curves (I_V s) for different gate voltages ranging from
 12 -10 to 10V. Gate leakage can be observed as an offset voltage from zero. (d) Transfer curves (I_{sd} vs.
 13 V_g) plotted in linear fashion. Note that for the transfer curve the leakage offset (seen in (c)) was
 14 subtracted to depict the behavior more clearly. (e) Wavelength dependence of the photocurrent

- 1 showing an enhanced photoresponse at the MoS₂ excitonic energies. For comparison the measured
- 2 differential reflectance spectrum of the MoS₂ flake prior transfer is added to the plot, relating A
- 3 (660nm) and B (610nm) exciton peaks to the peak responses in photocurrent measurements.
- 4